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MUĞLA

Meeting Agenda

SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists SMART

Host:Dumlupınar Primary School

**Venue:Emirbeyazıt Neighborhood, Ethem Serim Street No:15
Muğla, Türkiye**

Dates:07.10.2025-10.10.2025

07.10.2025 – Tuesday

- **09:00 – 09:30** → Welcome session at the host school
- **09:30 – 10:30** → Guided tour of the school facilities and meeting Logo Competition Winner
- **10:30-11:00**→ Coffee Break at School
- **11:00 – 11:30** → Visit to The District Director of National Education
- **11:30-13:00**→ Guided tour of Maturation Institute
- **13:00 – 14:30** → Lunch Break at school
- **16:00 – 18:30** → Walking tour along Muğla City
 - Yağcılar
 - Zahir Pazarı
 - Saburhane
- **19:30** → Dinner at the Pabuç Restaurant for all partners

08.10.2025 –Wednesday

- **09:00 – 10:00** →Lecture: “ Energy Savings and Energy Passport Preparation”
- **10:00-10:30** → Coffee Break at School
- **10:30-11:15**→ Workshop: Energy Passport Preparation
- **11:15 – 12:30** →Lecture: “Introducing Studies on Energy Savings”
- **12:30 – 13:30** → Lunch Break at school
- **14:00 – 18:00** → A trip to the Azmak River, famous for its cold river flowing into the sea and its clear water
 - Azmak Boat Tour
 - Forest Camping Trip

09.10.2025 – Thursday

- **09:00** → Köyceğiz – Dalyan Trip
- **09:00-09:15**→Get on the transfer vehicle
- **10:15-10:45**→Coffee Break with the view of Köyceğiz Lake
- **10:45-11:45**→Trip to Dalyan and entrance to the spa
- **11:45-12:30**→Mud bath in the spa
- **12:30 – 13:30** → Lunch at Paradise Restaurant
- **14:00 – 17:30** → İztuzu Beach and free time to swim
- **17:30-19:30**→Transfer to the restaurant where dinner will be served by transfer vehicles
- **19:30** → Dinner at the Olta Restaurant for all partners

10.10.2025 – Friday

- **09:30-10:30**→ Planning next steps in the project
- **10:30-11:00**→ Evaluation and reflection session
- **11:00-12:00**→ Certificate ceremony
- **12:00-12:15**→ Farewell and departure preparations

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